

First record of *Patapius spinosus* (Rossi, 1790) for Eastern Anatolia (Turkey) (Hemiptera: Leptopodidae)

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ABSTRACT: *Patapius spinosus* (Rossi, 1790) is recorded for the first time from Eastern Anatolia (Turkey). This species is widespread from Mediterranean to Central Asia, but in Turkey it was known until now only from the southern of Anatolia. This record is the eastern- and northern most one for Turkey.

KEYWORDS: *Patapius spinosus*, Eastern Turkey, first record

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INTRODUCTION

Leptopodidae is the family of spiny-legged bugs in the order Hemiptera. It includes 10 genera with 39 species.

Patapius spinosus (Rossi, 1790), a notable leptopodid bug whose body is covered with spines, was collected for the first time in Tunceli province (Turkey). In this area Fent et al. (2011), in their detailed study of aquatic Heteroptera, reported 100 species. Also Matocq et al. (2014) and Dioli et al. (2019) added other aquatic

species in South and East Anatolia, including Leptopodidae. In this article, we report the collection record and the distribution of *Patapius spinosus* (Rossi, 1790), in Eastern Turkey).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Material from East Anatolia was collected in the year 2018 from streams and their banks. The samples were collected by using a net and they were preserved in 70% ethanol. Specimens were identified

using Cobben (1968) by second author.

The recorded specimens are preserved in the collection of the Fırat University, Bioengineering Department, Elazığ (Turkey).

RESULTS

Patapius spinosus (Rossi, 1790) (Fig. 1).

Acanthia spinosa Rossi, 1790: 224

Material examined: Turkey, Tunceli, Karşılar village, 39°12'7" N 39°28'35" E, at Laç stream edge, 18.5.2018, 2 ♂, Totally: 2 exs. (Fig. 1), leg. Özgen & Topdemir.

Distribution in Turkey: Adana, Bursa, Denizli, Diyarbakır, İzmir, Siirt (Önder & Adıgüzel, 1979; Önder et al., 2006; Matocq et al., 2014, Fent et al., 2011).

Distribution in the World: A Ponto-Mediterranean species present in **Southern Europe:** Bulgaria, France, Greece, Italy, Macedonia, Spain, Portugal (Lindskog, 1995), Malta (Cuesta Segura et al., 2010), Slovenia (Gogala, 2003), Crete (Heckmann et al., 2015); European Turkey (Fent & Aktaş, 2008). In **North Africa** it was found in Algeria, Canary Islands, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia (Lindskog, 1995). In **Asia:** Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, Armenia, Asian Turkey, Cyprus, Georgia, Iraq, Israel, Kirgizia, Lebanon (Lindskog, 1995), Iran (Ghahari et al., 2013), Syria (Vinokurov & Kment, 2015), Tadzhikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan. It was also introduced in Japan (Yamazaki & Sugiura 2004), Western United States of America and Chile (Usinger, 1941; Lindskog, 1995; Aukema et al., 2013).

Figure 1. The Habitus of *Patapius spinosus* (Rossi, 1790). (Photos by İ., Özgen)

DISCUSSION

The genus *Patapius* Horváth, 1912 is easily distinguished by having the first and second antennal articles sub-equal in length and much larger than the subsequent ones, which, on the other hand, are very delicate and threadlike. The eyes generally carry clearly visible spines (Cobben, 1968; Pericart, 1990).

Patapius includes eight known species,

three of them are in the Palearctic region: *P. atapius spinosus* (Rossi, 1790) (Ponto-Mediterranean), *P. atapius sentus* Drake & Hoberlandt, 1951 (Egypt, Afghanistan, Iran and Israel) and *P. thaiensis* Cobben, 1968 (China and Thailand). The remaining species are afrotropical (Pericart, 1990; Lindskog, 1995).

The palearctic *Patapius* species, according to Cobben (1968) can be identified by the following key (modified, original):

Key to the species of Genus *Patapius* Horváth, 1912

1. Eyes with spines2
 - Eyes without spines..... ***P. thaiensis***
 2. Length about 2 mm. Spines on eyes short. External margin of corium not distinctly serrate ***P. sentus***
 - Length 3-3.5 mm. Spines on eyes conspicuous. External margin of corium distinctly serrate..... ***P. spinosus***

This species, as other Leptopodidae, is a predator of little arthropods but it can also be necrophagous (Baz et al., 2010; Baena, 2011). Generally it lives in hot and arid places with a certain preference for those altered by man such as roadsides and paths, rubble, piles of stones, almost always under them (Pericart, 1990). In North America (Zack et al., 2001) this bug was every time associated with the deposit of stones near to the roads that ran parallel to an alkaline pond or even colonized the underface of dried rocks (pile of basalt) that have been leaved after construction activities. In Spain (Baena & Vázquez, 1989) it was also captured under the dried bark of almond, plane tree, cypress and pine trees. Adult instars overwinter from December after mating and the life cycle starts again in the spring with the laying of the eggs. In Sardinia, two specimens were found near Senorbi (Cagliari, leg. C. Meloni) under a log, in a dry environment (Pericart, 1990).

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